

BCOMING

POLICY BRIEF

Biodiversity Conservation to Mitigate the Risks of Emerging Infectious Diseases

Implementation of One Health initiatives for better surveillance and mitigating the risks of emerging zoonotic diseases – participatory processes and technological tools supporting the successful results

**Funded by
the European Union**

Context

EU-funded BCOMING project received support under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-01-11 call. **Wildlife microbiomes**, whether symbiotic, commensal or pathogenic, and their potential to spread by crossing interspecies barriers, eventually reaching humans via transitional interfaces (e.g. peri-urban, farming areas), **are still largely unknown**.

Complex links between increased human-mediated disturbance, land-use change, natural habitat loss/degradation/fragmentation, climate change and biodiversity loss have all been linked to increases in the prevalence and risk of zoonotic disease for a variety of pathogens, mostly driven by human activities that modify the environment or spread pathogens into new ecological niches^{1,2}.

Zoonotic diseases are significant threats to human health, with vector-borne diseases accounting for approximately 17% of all infectious diseases and causing an estimated 700,000 deaths globally^{3,3} in a normal year, which can more than double in pandemic years.

The magnitude and direction of altered disease incidences due to anthropogenic disturbances differ globally and between ecosystems. Some described mechanisms and drivers that especially affect infectious disease risk are⁴ habitat alteration (e.g. deforestation, urbanisation), depletion of predators, biological invasion, host transfer, biodiversity change, human-driven genetic changes, bushmeat hunting and consumption, environmental contamination by infectious agents, international exchanges, trade, etc.

BCOMING is focusing on

BCOMING is focusing on biodiversity, its loss and maintenance, to reduce the risk of infectious disease emergence in the future. Activities will be applied in Europe and three tropical biodiversity hotspots. Deliverables anticipated include context-adapted biodiversity conservation and restoration strategies that reduce risk from zoonoses and improved capacity to prevent epidemics turning into pandemics.

Biodiversity loss in hotspots of biodiversity is, among other socio-ecological factors, **key to understand, prevent and react to future pandemics.**

However, despite this knowledge, the COVID-19 crisis highlighted the limitations of the implementation of One Health approaches. A main limitation is the lack of context-adapted solutions that stakeholders could easily implement on the field.

To overcome this, BCOMING is building on past international projects to co-construct innovations with all stakeholders of biodiversity hotspots to reduce the risk of infectious disease emergence through biodiversity conservation and disease surveillance strategies. The activities of the project are implemented in **Europe** and three tropical biodiversity hotspots in **Southeast Asia, West Africa and the Caribbean**.

 BCOMING will lead to a better understanding of the mechanisms underlying the impact of biodiversity on the risk of infectious disease emergence

 Participatory tools developed will facilitate the design of context-adapted biodiversity conservation and restoration strategies that reduce zoonotic risk

The surveillance strategies and pathogen detection tools developed will improve the capacities to detect emergences and stop future epidemics before they can turn into pandemics.

The embedment of BCOMING in the PREZODE initiative will help to scale up the project innovations and disseminate cutting-edge socio-economic environmental strategies.

The successful implementation of One Health strategies requires commitment from governments, organizations, and communities. Policy recommendations can serve as a foundation for promoting holistic health and well-being.

[1] [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)60901-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)60901-1)

[2] <https://www.cbd.int/health/SOK-biodiversity-en.pdf>

[3] <https://www.ipbes.net/global-assessment> and <https://www.ipbes.net/assessment-reports/ldr>

[4] Patz & Confalonieri (2005) Human Health: Ecosystem Regulation of Infectious Diseases. Ecosystems and Human Well-being: Current State and Trends. 1. cited in IPBES global assessment report, 2019

The present policy brief represents a synthesis of feedback from local stakeholders and those shared by the three NGOs (MERFI, FFI and iDE) actively supporting the One Health approach implementation in BCOMING. BCOMING is planning to formulate specific policy

recommendations depending on the context of the implementation of One Health approaches in the targeted tropical countries. It is recommended that relevant governmental organisations review this policy brief and embed it into the national context.

Evidence and Analysis

Pathogen Detection Tools

CRISPR (clustered regularly interspaced palindromic repeats) technology has been developed in the last years to detect a range of organisms. CRISPR has been used in research to identify species from tissue and environmental DNA within 2.5 hours⁵.

Nature Metrics (NM) is adapting the tools to detect invasive species in freshwater environments. Unlike current DNA-based detection platforms, the CRISPR approach can be equipment-free and can utilise pregnancy-test style flow-strips to indicate whether targeted species are present. This **simplicity of use, speed and high-accuracy of the technique enables access to new global markets** including the Emerging Infectious Disease Diagnostics market.

NM in BCOMING is building on Innovate UK MOSAIC Project, expediting the development of rapid in-field identification tools for zoonotic diseases to achieve TRL5-6 upon project completion (prototype tested in the field).

Participatory Tools

BCOMING is co-constructing biodiversity conservation strategies to enable local communities and decision makers to pilot innovative One Health solutions and mitigation actions based on a participatory evaluation of different management intervention scenarios.

Currently, natural resource conservation interventions do not reflect a One Health approach and as such do not prevent zoonotic disease emergence/spillover.

In the BCOMING project, **conservation strategies are co-constructed with local stakeholders** (users and decision makers) based on the One Health mitigation actions identified from the participatory ChaRL⁶ process (Challenge and Reconstruct Learning) and derived from their revised future visions. The participatory process will thus generate key context-adapted innovative solutions to implement biodiversity conservation actions while reducing zoonotic risk.

The general approach to support the co-construction of innovative solutions to mitigate zoonotic risks relies on an iterative participatory process and the use of agent-based models (BCOMING will develop seven case study agent-based models (ABMs) to support the co-construction of biodiversity conservation and restoration strategies specific to local ecological and socio-economical settings and known ecosystem services. The models will be adapted from existing ABMs (currently SRL 3 and SRL 6 at respectively local and regional scales). The visual representation of the spatially-referenced models will aid community understanding and address cognitive limitations of complex social-ecological systems.)⁷.

The ChaRL participatory visioning is a learning process that serves as a conceptual framework oriented to the governance, management and planning for One Health outcomes.

ChaRL allows stakeholders to test what is feasible and what is not. The process, designed by the Mekong Region Futures Institute (MERFI) has been regionally tested with numerous decision-making groups over the past 12 years⁸, including Cambodia.

[5] Baerwald, et al. Rapid and accurate species identification for ecological studies and monitoring using CRISPR-based SHERLOCK, Molecular Ecology Resources, 2020. Williams, et al. The application of CRISPR-Cas for single species identification from environmental DNA, Molecular Ecology Resources, 2019

[6] <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2013.07.002>

[7] [doi:10.1016/j.jenvsoft.2010.04.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvsoft.2010.04.008)

[8] <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-07421-200215>

The process involves a sequence of three workshops focusing on:

The existing and pending developments, aspirations and tensions between sectors and stakeholders

The causality between proposed developments, biodiversity regimes and zoonotic surveillance and the stated visions of the future

Enabling case study communities and decision-makers to discover actions to generate system-based mitigation for One Health problems and tensions.

Challenged and reconstructed beliefs encourage One Health systems learning, facilitating revised and plausible One Health mitigation actions. BCOMING will use the results of the ChaRL participatory process to assess the risk perception of actors who would use the surveillance system, their potential or actual involvement in the surveillance activities, and identify indicators to be monitored. **Innovative approaches rooted in social sciences**, such as stakeholder mapping, behavioural economics and participatory modelling, **will be used to identify the difficulties faced by local stakeholders** to engage in a change of practice, to define incentive schemes to overcome their obstacles, to analyse how stakeholders' decisions are made and what mechanisms drive their choices, and to co-construct a common and shared representation of the effective surveillance system.

Four interviews were organised in May 2024 with the three NGOs actively supporting the One Health approach implementation in BCOMING - International

Development Enterprises (iDE); Fauna and Flora International (FFI) Guinea and Cambodia; Mekong Region Futures Institute (MERFI) - focusing on **the identification of obstacles for participation in One-Health systems**, incentives and tools facilitating the involvement of local society and also the regulatory and policy actions that could help the implementation of surveillance activities on-site.

Observations were made on livelihoods, traditions, social behaviour and generational gaps and many other aspects on involvement and connectivity of local stakeholders.

It is anticipated that the final project results in BCOMING (agent-based models, ChaRL participatory process conclusions, eDNA rapid detection tools) will have a significant impact scientifically, but also in introducing successful One Health approaches and develop improved surveillance system validated both by local communities and decision-makers in tropical regions.

Key Policy Recommendations

More research and market investment is needed in rapid detection tools and tests for virus species on the field

New tools (multiplex serology and rapid CRISPR pathogen detection tools) to improve the detection capacities for emerging infectious diseases in tropical areas are developed in BCOMING. The project will develop a community of practice from the field to the wet laboratory, develop standardised pathogen (exposure) detection and characterisation tools and provide a much-needed template for organised efforts on this scale. These tools and the scientific evidence collected with them will be used to support the design of innovative surveillance strategies. Intellectual property (IP) protection will happen on CRISPR-based lateral flow devices to monitor environmental pathogens in water (rapid and on-site detection test for virus species in soil, water or wildlife). IP protection would encompass the system and process. All testing and sample use is happening in full compliance with the Nagoya protocol.

Participatory processes should be integrated into the implementation of One Health initiatives. Change should be implemented with the engagement of local communities, relevant authorities and policymakers following a set of specific steps

The first set of participatory workshops in BCOMING showed that the process of engaging the local actors and the process to elicit their causal beliefs is crucial. Raising awareness, education, incentives are just one part of the solution. Existing beliefs need to be challenged and reconstructed to encourage One Health systems learning and facilitate revised and plausible One Health mitigation actions. During the first participatory workshops, researchers, community stakeholders and local decision-makers revealed

potential motivating factors that could be activated to sustain participation and encourage surveillance reporting by community members and stakeholders.

Social incentives, regulations and financial/economic incentives identified during the participatory process were analysed.

The operation of the surveillance systems relies on inputs provided by case study stakeholders exposed to zoonotic risks. The willingness to systematically report data and provide information is a key factor of an operating One Health surveillance system. The attitudes of local stakeholders revealed during the initial activities of BCOMING have been analysed to define the local conditions for One Health strategies, and to detect barriers and incentives leading to a positive behavioural change.

Besides policy-science interface, it is crucial to encourage and fund civil society-science interface

Both researchers and NGOs reported that participating together in the project activities was beneficial for creating the common understanding of one-health related problems and solutions. Collaboration of researchers and companies from different scientific domains and sectors is considered beneficial. Capturing the perspectives of NGOs working in the field with local communities, with an aim of achieving behavioural change, is crucial for testing and validating the research methodologies, and developed technological tools geared to sustainability and long-term use. Use of the research and technological results will be ensured through participatory processes. Such collaboration will result in proper adaptation of One Health strategies to national contexts, aligned with the policies of bodies responsible for One Health approaches, biodiversity conservation and disease surveillance systems.

Project name

Biodiversity Conservation to Mitigate the risks of emerging infectious diseases (BCOMING)

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Website

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